

A variance reduction approach for adjoint weighted tallies in a super-history scheme

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we study the effect of using branchless collisions and implicit leakage on the variance of adjoint flux estimate with the example of adjoint weighted tallies. Adjoint weighted tallies are commonly encountered in Monte Carlo production level code for computing effective kinetic parameters and sensitivity coefficient. In criticality Monte Carlo calculations, the adjoint function is usually estimated as the number of progeny after a given number of latent generations for a neutron inserted in the system. This estimate may induce variance in the sensitivity coefficients estimate, especially when the number of latent generation grows. These methods are tested on two simple one dimension single speed configurations showing an improvement on the estimated standard error and figure of Merit, especially for the branchless in the case of a large (in terms of mean free path) configuration.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, sensitivities, variance reduction, branchless

1. INTRODUCTION

Adjoint weighted tallies have become a standard feature in production level Monte Carlo codes for computing k-eigenvalue sensitivities or effective kinetic parameters, for instance see the review [1]. Most of the sensitivity calculations methods rely on propagating an information over several generations in a fission chain. For instance, adjoint weighted tallies require an estimation of the progeny induced by a neutron after a given number of generations [2]; or the Differential Operator Sampling together with a source perturbation which accumulates the effect of the perturbation from the ancestors over several generations up to the current particle [3].

The propagation of this information over several generations can usually be achieved by some book-keeping techniques (e.g. using the Iterated Fission Probability [2]) which requires storage over several cycles, or by simulating fission chains in the current cycle (e.g. using a super-history scheme [4]). These techniques allow us to choose between memory occupation or computing time when performing sensitivity calculations.

Let us focus, for the present paper, on k_{eff} sensitivities computed using the adjoint weighted form with a super-history powering scheme. Generally, computing an adjoint estimate as the progeny after L generations (also referred as latent generations) will yield to a large variability as L grows because some fission chains will extinct before L generations and some may grow to a large population. This may contribute to convergence difficulties when estimating sensitivities with large L latent generations values observed for instance in [5].

In this paper, we will evaluate the effect of using branchless collision and implicit leakage variance reduction techniques in the frame of sensitivity coefficients calculations. These tests will be performed

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using a simple configuration, a one dimensional critical slab with a single particle speed, allowing for the development of a Monte Carlo mock-up embedding all techniques. The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the configuration data, Section 3 details the methods used in the present study and Section 4 exhibits and discusses the results.

2. SIMPLE SLAB CONFIGURATIONS

In order to test the use of branchless and implicit leakage strategies, we used a one dimensional slab with a single speed. Two configurations have been used for these tests. The first configuration is a leakage dominated system denoted "small" afterwards, because it is quite small compared to the mean free path and is dominated by leakage. The second system is a large system compared to the mean free path with a quite low leakage fraction, it is denoted "large" in the rest of the paper. Tests will be performed at criticality as most of sensitivity calculations are performed around criticality.

The configurations characteristics have been built from the slab configuration Ua-1-0-SL of [6]. The small configuration directly uses these data while the large configuration uses a larger slab width and the same cross section dataset with the exception of the fission yield that was rescaled in order to preserve a critical configuration. The configurations data are summed up in Table I with Σ_r being the usual macroscopic cross section of reaction r and ν being the fission yield. In this configuration, the scattering yield is one and thus is not written explicitly. The outgoing scattering and fission distributions are isotropic.

Table I. Nuclear Data and slab size for the two studies configurations.

Configuration	half-width	Σ_t	Σ_s	Σ_c	Σ_f	ν
Small	2.872934	0.32640	0.248064	0.013056	0.065280	2.70
Large	50.0	0.32640	0.248064	0.013056	0.065280	2.70 / 2.22376

The small system has a leakage fraction of 0.55541 ± 0.00010 while the large system has an estimated leakage fraction of 0.01168 ± 0.00002 . These leakage fractions have been estimated using a Monte Carlo code with an analog simulation; i.e. particle weights are exactly 1.0 along the entire simulation.

3. METHODS

The notation assumes the context of a one dimension finite slab configuration, which is the test case considered in this paper and described in Section 2.

3.1. Sensitivity coefficients

In the adjoint weighted formulation, the sensitivity coefficient of k_{eff} to a parameter p (for instance a cross section) express as:

$$S(p) = \frac{p}{k} \frac{\partial k}{\partial p} = \frac{\langle \varphi^\dagger \partial_p \mathcal{A} \varphi \rangle}{\langle \varphi^\dagger \frac{1}{k} \mathcal{F} \varphi \rangle} \quad (1)$$

where $\partial_p \mathcal{A}$ is the scaled partial derivative of the collision, scattering and fission operators, φ^\dagger the adjoint flux, φ the direct flux [7] and k denotes the apparent multiplication factor of the system. The fundamental adjoint function can be related to the neutron importance in the system which is proportional to the asymptotic progeny of a neutron. Thus, it may be estimated by recording the descendants after L latent generations for an particle injected into the system at coordinates \mathbf{r}, Ω, E ; which will yield on average

$$\pi = \prod_{m=1}^M \frac{\nu\sigma_{f,\alpha}(z_m)}{\sigma_a(z_m)} = \sum_{i \in M} \omega_i \quad (2)$$

neutrons at a latent generation M . ω_i denotes the weight of the neutrons at generation L . This can be directly estimated during the simulation in a super-history powering scheme [8] where the neutron population evolves over several generations without normalization.

3.2. Implicit leakage

In case of a finite system with vacuum boundary condition, and when the system is dominated by leakage, numerous particles will leave out of the system without contributing to the adjoint flux estimate. For instance, in the small system considered here, around 55% of all particles simulated in a given batch will escape the system. When using the super-history method, which often applies no population normalization technique, this leakage may yield a lot of null contributions, especially when the number of latent generations increases. Implicit leakage, see section 3.II.A. of [9], consists of replacing actual particle escape by weight modification. Then, the distance to the next collision probability density function (pdf) becomes

$$\hat{p}(\ell) = \frac{p(\ell)}{1 - p_{leak}} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{with } p_{leak} = \exp(-\Sigma_t \ell_{leak}) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{and } p(\ell) = \Sigma_t \exp(-\Sigma_t \ell) \quad (5)$$

where p_{leak} is the leakage probability and ℓ_{leak} is the distance to the boundary with vacuum condition. Notations are taken for the simplified configuration considered in this paper. When modifying this pdf, the particle weight is corrected by the non leakage probability :

$$1 - p_{leak} = 1 - \exp(-\Sigma_t \ell_{leak}) \quad (6)$$

3.3. Branchless collision

In a super-history powering, when the number of latent generations grows, fission chains differ, grow or shrink and may yield very different progeny leading to larger variance as the number of latent generations grows. Branchless sampling of collisions, see section 5.III.C of [9], consists of generating exactly one particle coming out of collision events and selecting a reaction channel, either scattering or fission in the present configuration, according to the following probabilities

$$p_s = \frac{\Sigma_s}{\Sigma_s + \nu\Sigma_f} \quad p_f = \frac{\nu\Sigma_f}{\Sigma_s + \nu\Sigma_f} \quad (7)$$

It should be noted that in the present configuration, there is no yield in front of the scattering cross section as it is implicitly unity. With these probabilities, the weight correction writes

$$\frac{\Sigma_s + \nu\Sigma_f}{\Sigma_t} \quad (8)$$

3.4. Population control

With the use of branchless collisions and implicit leakage, particles become immortal as sterile capture cannot be sampled and particles cannot leak out of the system. So there has to be some population control mechanism for the simulation to end. First, the super-history method actually contains a population control mechanism in the sense that it will stop fission chains after a given number of generations which are related by fission events. However, this may yield very long particle histories with a large range of particle statistical weights. To limit this behavior, we used the usual combination of splitting and Russian roulette. The parameters are the following: the splitting threshold is 4.0, the post-splitting target weight is 1.0, the roulette threshold is 0.25 and the survival target weight is 1.0. The population control choice of parameters may largely impact the variance and computing time, however due to the paper length limit its study is left for future work.

4. SENSITIVITIES TO NUCLEAR DATA

In order to generate reference solutions, we wrote a mock-up S_n transport code using description of chapter 8 from [10]. This code allowed us to compute reference k_{eff} values and estimate “reference” sensitivities values with a direct perturbation approach. Sensitivity coefficients values are obtained by averaging sensitivity coefficients obtained through a positive and negative perturbation of cross section by 0.1%. This perturbation value has been verified to provide consistent estimate by varying this perturbation from 0.01% to 0.5%.

As customary, we will use the Figure of Merit (FoM) to evaluate the performance, with σ denoting the standard error and T the computing time.

$$\text{FoM} = \frac{1}{\sigma^2 T} \quad (9)$$

Because computing time is subject to many variations (implementation details, machine used for running the tests, ...) the FoM only makes sense in a relative form. Thus, all FoMs presented below are displayed relatively to the analog collision and analog leakage calculation of the exact same configuration, i.e. number of latent generations simulated in the super-history.

4.1. The small configuration

The S_n calculations were performed using a Gauss order of 64 and a spatial discretization of 200 bins. The Monte Carlo calculations were performed with 20 000 neutrons per cycle, 250 cycles, and a discard of 10 cycles.

Table II displays the results of sensitivity coefficients calculations for the small configuration. Monte Carlo calculations are computed using 10 latent generations in the super-history scheme. The Monte Carlo estimates are consistent with the direct perturbation calculation. All combinations of analog or branchless collision and analog or implicit leakage lie within the three standard error confidence interval.

Figure 1 displays the evolution of the standard error and the normalized Figure of Merit as a function of the number of latent generations for the sensitivity coefficients to fission cross section; although scattering and capture has also been studied it is not displayed here due to page limitation. In the legends, the first (second) term refers to the collision (leakage) sampling method.

One can observe a very similar trend between the three sensitivity coefficients. The standard error grows linearly with the number of latent generations. The slope of the increase is smaller when using the implicit leakage compared to the analog leakage. The use of branchless collision seems to have a slight effect combined with the implicit leakage although it is not very clear. However, when looking at the relative FoM, we can observe that the analog collision with the implicit leakage is actually less

Table II. Small configuration sensitivity coefficients obtained by direct perturbation of the S_n solver and Monte Carlo calculations with all combinations using analog or branchless collisions and analog or implicit leakage with 10 latent generations.

Cross Section	Direct Perturbation with S_n solver	Analog coll. Analog leak.	Branchless Analog leak.	Analog coll. Implicit leak.	Branchless Implicit leak.
Fission	0.65472	0.65543 ± 0.00071	0.65468 ± 0.00074	0.65379 ± 0.00052	0.65605 ± 0.00045
Scattering	0.09524	0.09277 ± 0.00233	0.09153 ± 0.00252	0.09770 ± 0.00184	0.09618 ± 0.00144
Capture	-0.06906	-0.06891 ± 0.00014	-0.06906 ± 0.00015	-0.06924 ± 0.00010	-0.06879 ± 0.00009

efficient than the analog collision and leakage. The branchless strategy improves the FoM due to the fact that using branchless collision implies simulating less particles, hence, simulations are faster with respect to analog collisions. The most efficient strategy in this case seems to be the branchless collision with implicit leakage with an increase of a factor about 3 in terms of FoM.

Figure 1. Sensitivity to fission cross section as a function of the number of latent generations for the small configuration.

4.2. The large configuration

The S_n calculations were performed using a Gauss order of 64 and a spatial discretization of 1000 bins. Monte Carlo calculations were run using 20 000 neutrons per cycle, 350 cycles and a discard of 50 cycles. Table III displays the results of sensitivity coefficients calculations for the large configuration, using 10 latent generations in the super-history scheme. The Monte Carlo estimates are consistent with the direct perturbation calculation as they all lie within the three standard error confidence interval.

Figures 2 and 3 display the evolution of the standard error and the normalized Figure of Merit as a function of the number of latent generations, respectively for the sensitivity coefficients with respect to fission and scattering cross sections; capture has also been studied but not displayed here. In the legends, the first (second) term refers to the collision (leakage) sampling method.

One can observe a very similar trend between the three sensitivity coefficients. The standard error grows linearly with the number of latent generations for the analog sampling of the collision. When

Table III. Large configuration sensitivity coefficients obtained by direct perturbation of the S_n solver and Monte Carlo calculations with all combinations using analog or branchless collisions and analog or implicit leakage with 10 latent generations.

Cross Section	Direct Perturbation with S_n solver	Analog coll. Analog leak.	Branchless Analog leak.	Analog coll. Implicit leak.	Branchless Implicit leak.
Fission	0.17847	0.17846 ± 0.00068	0.17812 ± 0.00037	0.17860 ± 0.00071	0.17778 ± 0.00032
Scattering	0.00803	0.00752 ± 0.00169	0.00764 ± 0.00083	0.00704 ± 0.00151	0.00890 ± 0.00071
Capture	-0.16431	-0.16431 ± 0.00014	-0.16438 ± 0.00007	-0.16428 ± 0.00014	-0.16444 ± 0.00006

considering the branchless strategy, the standard error seems to slightly grows linearly but with a very low slope rendering it almost constant when compared to the analog game. The use of implicit leakage seems to have almost no effect on the behavior of the standard error, probably due to the fact that only about 1% of particles escape this system. The gain in FoM seems to grow (almost) linearly with the number of latent generations. This is due to the computing time which grows linearly as a function of the number of simulated generation in each cycle. Thus, we observe FoM gain ranging from 5 to 25. We can observe several outliers in terms of FoM (coming from the computing time). The root cause of these outliers have not been identified yet.

(a) Standard error.

(b) FoM normalized to analog collision and leakage case.

Figure 2. Sensitivity to fission cross section as a function of the number of latent generations for the large configuration.

In order to complement the analysis, Figure 4 displays the scalar adjoint flux shape estimated using the four combinations. The scalar adjoint flux was computed every 2 cm using 10 000 neutrons starting at each location with 30 latent generations between the starting particles and the adjoint estimate. We can observe that the use of the branchless method provides a much lower relative standard error. The ratio between the fully analog version and the branchless and implicit leakage version relative standard errors goes from 3 to 9 according to the location. This is a quite interesting gain in estimating the adjoint flux.

Figure 3. Sensitivity to scattering cross section as a function of the number of latent generations for the large configuration.

Figure 4. Monte Carlo scalar adjoint flux estimate and its relative standard error as a function of the position. 30 latent generations are used to compute the adjoint flux.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Two variance reduction methods, branchless collision and implicit leakage, were tested on a very simple configuration in order to try reducing the variability of adjoint function estimate. In the context of a large configuration (compared to the mean free path), it appears that using the branchless collision leads to a quite interesting gain in terms of both standard error and FoM which gain goes from 5 to 35 as the number of latent generations increases for the observed cross section sensitivities. For this configuration where the leakage fraction is quite small (about 1%), the implicit leakage method has no effect. On the hand, for the leakage dominated configuration, the use of branchless collisions offers a small improvement in the Figure of Merit; especially when combined to the implicit leakage where a factor 2 to 4 is observed. The implicit leakage model improves the standard error for both analog and

branchless collisions. However, analog collision with implicit leakage has a smaller Figure of Merit compared to all other combination. Overall, the branchless collision method seems to offer the best improvement, especially in the case of large systems whereas the implicit leakage offers smaller standard errors in leakage dominated systems. It would be interesting to look at the behavior of the variance of the adjoint flux estimate as a function of the number of generations and extends to three dimensional systems.

However, this conclusion needs to be further substantiate to a real-world application, with for instance a full scale PWR reactor model. In particular, the efficiency of the branchless strategy can greatly differ due to implementation details (e.g. material wise or nuclide wise branchless) and have a large impact on the computing time. In addition, it would be worthy to investigate the effect of the population control parameters on the efficiency of this method as well as varying the k_{eff} value around criticality to study the behavior when the system is slightly non critical which is the most encountered case in real life applications. Finally, it would be interesting to extend this branchless approach for the Differential Operator Sampling with source perturbation for generalized perturbation methods applied to reaction rate ratio or effective kinetic parameters [4].

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